

Particle position prediction

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Abstract—In this report, we introduce a possible approach to the task of detecting the positions where particles pass in their trajectories which is one of the long-standing tasks within the field of particle physics. In particular, the proposed approach consists in retrieving all available information from the characteristics of the signals measured by the pads of a sensor for each event, referring to the passage of a particle through the sensor, and analyzing the dataset in order to use just the most informative part of it. Then, by using it as input for regression modeling, we propose a model capable of predicting for each event, the 2D coordinates where the particle of interest passed while obtaining overall satisfactory results.

I. PROBLEM OVERVIEW

The proposed task is a multi-output regression problem on a dataset containing events in tabular format. It counts 514.000 entries, each of which refers to an event expressed in terms of the characteristics of the signals measured by each of the pads of the sensor. The purpose of the task is to correctly predict the position (the 2D coordinates) where the particle of interest passed associated with an event. The dataset is divided into two parts:

- A development set containing 385,500 events, for which the 2D coordinates are given;
- An evaluation set containing the remaining 128,500 events.

We will need to use the development set to build a multi-output regression model that correctly predicts the 2D coordinates for each event in the evaluation set. We can make some considerations based on the development set: The problem we have is a multivariate multi-output regression problem with only quantitative variables. So, for the sake of understanding the relationship between the features and the response variable which is in our case the 2D coordinates, our first step is to Pearson Correlation check. The correlation is a measure of the linear relationship of 2 or more variables through which, we can predict one variable from the other. The logic behind using correlation for feature selection is twofold:

- The good variables are highly correlated with the target
- By calculating the correlation coefficient between pairs of predictive features, we can identify features that may be contributing to multicollinearity.

The correlation map, as shown in Figure 1, shows how our numerical features are correlated with the 2D coordinates of the particles. In particular, we have the following information:

- features correlated with x: pmax[1] (0.727), area[1] (0.701), pmax[8] (0.779), area[8] (0.765), pmax[13] (0.661), area[13] (0.658), pmax[14] (0.679), area[14] (0.668)

- features correlated with y: pmax[3] (0.704), area[3] (0.691), pmax[4] (0.761), area[4] (0.701), pmax[10] (0.659), area[10] (0.646), pmax[11] (0.714), area[11] (0.700)

For the sake of quantifying the multicollinearity indicated by the correlation map, we decided to endorse our check with a second metric for gauging multicollinearity which is the **variance inflation factor (VIF)**. The VIF directly measures the ratio of the variance of the entire model to the variance of a model with only the underlying feature. That is, In layman's terms, it gauges how much a feature's inclusion contributes to the overall variance of the coefficients of the features in the model. A VIF of 1 indicates that the feature does not correlate with any of the other features. Typically, a VIF value exceeding 5 or 10 is deemed to be too high. Any feature with such VIF values is likely to be contributing to multicollinearity. Since the input features are characteristics of signals, we found it intriguing to perform some feature engineering by adding new features, transforming existing ones, and selecting the most relevant attributes to help the model understand the data's underlying patterns, relationships, and nuances which will, therefore, improve its predictive performance.

Fig. 1

II. II. PROPOSED APPROACH

(a) Data Pre-Processing

- **Missing Values**, there are no missing values in our Dataset which comes in handy for the rest of the analysis
- **Outliers removal** Although we have a lot of outliers in our dataset, we decided to keep them and use them for the analysis and prediction as this would make the model more robust since in the real world, we will always encounter outliers.
- **Feature Engineering**
 - **Remove Multicollinear Features** As shown in the table below, tmax_15_, tmax_17_, pmax_5_, area_5_ , and pmax_3_’ all have VIF values exceeding 5. The rookie mistake would be to remove all features at once. Feature selection is usually best performed by including or removing one feature at a time. This ensures that any information loss is minimized.

	Variable	VIF
3	tmax_15_	163.674
0	tmax_17_	158.389
1	pmax_5_	23.898
12	area_5_	21.450
5	pmax_3_	5.616
14	pmax_2_	4.661
10	pmax_1_	4.212
13	pmax_4_	4.152
4	pmax_13_	4.074
6	pmax_11_	3.987
9	pmax_6_	3.779
8	pmax_14_	3.661
2	pmax_10_	3.563
11	pmax_9_	3.458
7	pmax_8_	2.816

So, let’s go ahead and remove the first feature tmax_15_ (i.e. the feature with the highest VIF) then calculate the VIF values again:

	Variable	VIF
0	tmax_17_	1.001
1	pmax_5_	22.751
2	pmax_10_	3.449
3	pmax_13_	2.593
4	pmax_3_	5.250
5	pmax_11_	3.299

Next, by computing the VIF values 2 more times and removing respectively pmax_5_ e pmax_3_,

we get the following VIF values:

	Variable	VIF
0	tmax_17_	1.001
1	pmax_10_	3.019
2	pmax_13_	2.570
3	pmax_11_	2.962
4	pmax_8_	2.707
5	pmax_14_	2.773
6	pmax_6_	2.624
7	pmax_1_	3.961
8	pmax_9_	2.609
9	area_5_	2.787
10	pmax_4_	3.568
11	pmax_2_	3.407

Now that the variance inflation factors are all within the acceptable range, the derived model will be more likely to yield statistically significant results since multicollinearity has little bearing on a model’s predictive performance.

- **Adding New Features** One of the main features when it comes to signal characteristics is the so-called **peak to peak** which is the difference between the highest and the lowest values in a waveform. We’ve seen that adding these features, to all of the sensor pads, improved the predictive performance.

(b) Model selection

We consider and analyze three different regressors, the linear regression, the SVR, and the linear SVR, so to understand if our data have either a possible linear behavior or not.

We remember once again that, to evaluate the performance of our model, we will split the development set into a training set and a test set.

- **Linear Regression**, a very simple and easily interpretable regressor that fits a linear model to minimize the residual sum of squares between the observed targets in the dataset and the targets predicted by the linear approximation. It is reasonably fast but not optimal for large amounts of data. With the data pre-processing steps, mentioned above, we’ve found a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.987$ which suggests a strong linear relationship between the explanatory variables and the target variable. Furthermore, all the assumptions of the linear regression model are satisfied including the assumptions on the residuals as shown in Figure 2:

Fig. 2

Last but not least, the only thing we're left with is to check the heteroscedasticity of the errors which can be done using the Goldfeld Quandt Test, defined as follows:

H_0 : Error terms are homoscedastic

vs

H_1 : Error terms are not homoscedastic

Since p-value is 0.996 (more than 0.05), we can't reject the null hypothesis H_0 . Therefore, the error terms are homoscedastic.

- **SVR, Support Vector Machine for Regression.** It is more complex than Linear Regression, but it usually holds the best accuracy measures. It is not an interpretable regressor and, above all, it suffers from the curse of dimensionality.
- **LinearSVR**, similar to SVR but with parameter kernel set to 'linear'. This regressor should scale better to large amounts of data (i.e. it is faster than SVR in general) without losing in terms of accuracy.
- **Decision Trees (DTs)**, analyze the input features and filter the dataset based on feature values such that the remaining data points are the ones that provide the maximum information about the target variable. Although they're very intuitive and simple in terms of their interpretability but Decision Trees easily overfit as they can create a tree that perfectly classifies the training data but performs poorly on the test data
- **Random Forest**, offers an improvement over the Decision Tree. A significant problem with decision trees is overfitting the training data making them susceptible to poor performance in unseen scenarios. Random Forest solves this problem by training a collection of decision trees on a subset of the data.
- **Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)** is an advanced implementation of the gradient boosting algorithm which is a machine learning technique where the main idea is to combine many simple models, also known as "weak learners," to create an ensemble model that is better at prediction. The XG Boosting algorithm uses advanced regularization techniques to suppress weights, prevent overfitting, and enhance its performance in real-world scenarios. On top of this, the implementation allows the algorithm to cache data and utilize multiple CPU cores for speedy processing.

By performing a general analysis with all the regressors trained and tested on the development set, we can assert that:

- As expected, in our setting the SVR approach is not implementable due to important hardware limitations and large dimensions of the provided dataset. Indeed, even if we could reach some good performance measures, it would require a very large amount of time. For this reason, we decide to analyze the LinearSVR instead since it is less general than SVR, but faster and, also, still a very good model;
- Linear regression did good but not good enough to beat the baseline;
- With Decision Trees, we've reached a good result with respect to both linear regression and LinearSVR which opened the road to trying ensemble methods;
- By trying Random Forest, without any fine-tuning, we've reached a score of 5.771 on the Leaderboard

(c) Hyperparameters tuning

Here, we've decided to tune the hyperparameters of only **XGBoost** (We've omitted Random Forest due to lack of time and hardware limitations).

To perform hyperparameter-tuning on **XGBoost**, we decided first of all to go step by step as we knew beforehand that the process would be time-consuming. Most of the parameters that are provided to XGBoost via the native API are defined in a dictionary. So, we started by defining the model with default values (a list and a description of all parameters here). The first that we decided to look at is not part of the parameters dictionary but basically passed as a standalone argument to the training process. This parameter is called **num_boost_round** and corresponds to the number of boosting rounds or trees that should be built. The only issue with this parameter is that its optimal value is highly correlated with the other parameters which means that it should be re-tuned each time we update any of the parameters. We could do this by tuning it together with all parameters in a grid search, but it requires a lot of computational effort. To do so, we define a test dataset and a metric that is used to assess performance at each round. If performance hasn't improved for M rounds (M is defined by the variable **early_stopping_round**), we stop the training and keep the best number of boosting rounds. Here is how works:

- First, we need to add the evaluation metric we are interested in, into our dictionary of parameters.
- We still need to pass a **num_boost_round** which corresponds to the maximum number of boosting rounds that we allow. We set it to a large value hoping to find the optimal number of rounds before reaching it if we haven't improved performance on our test dataset in **early_stopping_round** rounds
- To automatically find the best number of boosting rounds, we need to provide extra parameters on top

of the dictionary of the parameters, in particular, the so-called **early_stopping_rounds** which is the number of rounds without improvements after which we should stop,

By running the model with these parameters, we stopped before reaching the maximum number of boosting rounds, that's because after the 774th tree, adding more rounds did not lead to improvements in RMSE on the test dataset

	train-rmse-mean	train-rmse-std	test-rmse-mean	test-rmse-std
774	2.909477	0.012943	4.665573	0.050859

Training the model with 775 Trees led us to a score of 5.528 on the leaderboard.

The next move was to tune the other hyperparameters of the model and for that matter, we used the **cv** function from XGBoost that allows us to run cross-validation on our training dataset and return a mean RMSE score. **cv** returns a table where the rows correspond to the number of boosting trees used.

The last thing we had to try was applying grid search on these parameters simultaneously: **subsample** and **colsample_bytree**.

The reason behind this move is that these parameters control the sampling of the dataset that is done at each boosting round. Instead of using the whole training set every time, we can build a tree on slightly different data at each step, which makes it less likely to overfit to a single sample or feature.

- **subsample** corresponds to the fraction of observations (the rows) to subsample at each step. By default, it is set to 1 meaning that we use all rows.
- **colsample_bytree** corresponds to the fraction of features (the columns) to use. By default, it is set to 1 meaning that we will use all features.

The operation took so long and we had to run it on GPU. Fortunately, XGBoost provides a nice way to find the best number of rounds while training. Since trees are built sequentially, instead of fixing the number of rounds at the beginning, we can test our model at each step and see if adding a new tree/round improves performance.

With **subsample** and **colsample_bytree** fixed, we decided to perform a further grid search with the parameters listed in Table I. The reason was an attempt to obtain a fine-tuned model with improved predictive capabilities.

TABLE I: Hyperparameters Grid Search

Parameter	Values
<i>eta</i>	0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.05, 0.01, 0.005
<i>max_depth</i>	9, 10, 11
<i>min_child_weight</i>	5, 6, 7

III. RESULTS

The best configuration of the parameters obtained during the hyperparameter tuning stage was used on the data with and without feature engineering. The outputs are:

- Without Feature Engineering

```
[24] Test-rmse:324.93864
...
[2996] Test-rmse:3.70799
[2997] Test-rmse:3.70780
[2998] Test-rmse:3.70779
[2999] Test-rmse:3.70776
Output is truncated. View as a scrollable element or open in a text editor. Adjust cell output settings..
```

corresponding to a score of 4.621 on the Leaderboard

- With Feature Engineering

```
[24] Test-rmse:324.93253
...
[9319] Test-rmse:3.53201
[9320] Test-rmse:3.53201
[9321] Test-rmse:3.53200
[9322] Test-rmse:3.53201
Output is truncated. View as a scrollable element or open in a text editor. Adjust cell output settings..
```

corresponding to a score of 4.433 on the Leaderboard.

IV. DISCUSSION

By looking at our analysis, we can state that the most important part of the work is surely the data preprocessing. Indeed, although the final result is satisfying, some aspects might be worth considering to further improve the obtained results in both: accuracy and speed

- Analyzing all steps of data preprocessing including the part of the outliers that should be handled with care
- Running a more thorough grid search process over the set of hyperparameters to achieve a better configuration
- Trying different models with corresponding hyperparameters tuning

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